

Directed Neutrosophic Graph using Morphological Operators and Its Applications

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Abstract. Connectedness provides well suited solutions for several application problems. In Graph theory, graph is connected when there exist a path between any two arbitrary vertices. Neutrosophic set theory together with Morphological operators are useful for constructing the Neutrosophic directed connected subgraphs (NDCS). Using NDCS, method to generate an ordering of subgraphs and construction of spanning trees is presented in this paper. \mathcal{M} induced vertex sequences and \mathcal{M} induced Edge sequences are defined. These sequences generate spanning tree filtration of the graph. Algorithms are given for obtaining such filtrations. Directed Neutrosophic Morphological Network (DNG-MN) is defined. The spanness of a Neutrosophic graph induced by Morphological dilation is given in the paper. Some applications of these concepts are also discussed in this paper.

Keywords: Connected directed graphs, Morphological dilation, erosion, \mathcal{M} induced edge and vertex sequence. Neutrosophic directed graph, Directed Neutrosophic Graph Morphological Network (DNG-MN).

Literature Survey

A Fuzzy Graph is a type of graph such that each edge and vertex in the graph labeled with membership degree, representing uncertainty in the relation between vertices [18]. Uncertainty can be modeled using fuzzy set theory [20–23, 25], Intuitionistic fuzzy set theory [1], Neutrosophic sets etc. The Neutrosophic Graph is a generalization of the Fuzzy Graph. Neutrosophic Sets and graph [27] provide essential tools for analyzing ambiguous or imprecise information. Concepts like Fuzzy and Neutrosophic Sets with graph theory plays an important role in the

modeling of this type of information. These models are widely examined in the literature [1–4]. This will extend classical graph theory by adopting Neutrosophic sets which will be helpful for the modeling of ambiguous and complex relationships.

Product Perspective from Fuzzy to Neutrosophic Graph Extension was studied in [34]. Bathusha et.al presented the Energy of dominating single valued Neutrosophic graph structure and was studied in [32]. Fujita et.al studied various types of Neutrosophic graphs and super hyper tree [31], [33]. Bino et.al studied about the Morphological operators and filtering of Hypergraphs [8, 9, 29]. This paper also addresses the various morphological operators [2, 4, 28] which are applied on a Neutrosophic graph framework. Abraham et.al defined the morphological operators on Intuitionistic fuzzy soft graphs [12]. Dhanya et al. Studied the algebra of morphological operators [29] on intuitionistic hypergraph and its application using Neutrosophic hypergraph [13–18]. Sujatha Ramalingam et.al applied the span integrity of fuzzy graph on brain network analysis [3]. Further, this framework has been extended into Directed Neutrosophic Graph Morphological Network (DNG-MN) framework. \mathcal{M} induced edge sequences and vertex sequences are introduced in the paper. Based on these sequences, spanning tree filtrations are obtained. Algorithms for constructing spanning trees [5–7, 19, 20] are extended by considering the new framework. Practical applications are mentioned [24, 26] for further analysis which will help to increase the efficiency of the existing decision making algorithms.

1. Introduction

Graph theory, describes relationships and interconnections within the graph by considering the vertices (nodes) and edges. Graph provides essential insights into connectivity between vertices. Several application problems can be modeled using graph theory. Recently Graph theory concepts are applied in artificial intelligence. Subgraphs of a graph can be constructed using Morphological vertex dilation and erosion [2, 12, 27]. There are disjoint subgraphs such that in a connected graph there exist path between any two arbitrary vertices. So there exist common vertices and edges in these subgraphs. We are dealing with Neutrosophic graph and its underlying graph and subgraphs. Neutrosophic set theory and logic plays an important role in decision making problems. Eigen values of adjacency matrices corresponding to truth degree, indeterminacy degree and falsity degree of a Neutrosophic subgraphs obtained by taking the vertex dilation is computed. By comparing these eigen values, Neutrosophic graph modification can be performed. After applying the pairwise comparison of sum of membership degrees, direction can be assigned to edges. Algorithms are given for these constructions. The same procedure with different morphological operator like erosion will generate another modified Neutrosophic graph. This lead to the generalized framework for performing similar

construction of modified Neutrosophic graph. This is given as a system namely Neutrosophic directed Morphological Network. Algorithms for finding spanning trees of this network system are given. Such a spanning tree may be optimal. Spanning tree filtrations are important in several application problems. Edge sequences and vertex sequences are obtained by considering edges and vertices which are common to the sets of subgraphs. By including these sequences to the system, it can be considered as a Generalized Directed Neutrosophic Graph Morphological Network (DNG-MN) systems. Spanning tree which satisfying optimality conditions of this system can be considered in application problems like brain diseases. Span integrity and spanness of dilation induced vertex deleted graphs are calculated. It is useful for ordering the subgraphs. Algorithms are given for the construction of such systems.

1.1. Construction of connected subgraphs

Consider a Neutrosophic Graph G as shown in Fig. 1, with neutrosophic weights (membership, indeterminacy, non-membership) (μ, γ, κ) for each vertex in G . The edges are also having the three weights (μ, γ, κ) where for the edge e_{ij} between vertices v_i and v_j , the membership weight of the edge represented as $\mu_{e_{ij}}$ is the max (μ_{v_i}, μ_{v_j}) , the indeterminacy weight of the edge represented as γ_{ij} is the avg $(\gamma_{v_i}, \gamma_{v_j})$ and non-membership weight of the edge represented as $\kappa_{e_{ij}}$ is the min $(\kappa_{v_i}, \kappa_{v_j})$.

FIGURE 1. Neutrosophic graph G

Let v be any vertex in V . Find the Neutrosophic graph dilation $N_{\delta_G}(v)$ of v . Let $N_{\delta_G}(v_i) = NG_i$ and the underlying graph be G_i . Similarly, for any v_i , we get the underlying subgraphs G_i . Fig. 2 shows the subgraph $NG_1 = \delta(v_1)$.

Find the adjacency matrix $A(NG_1)$ of the subgraphs NG_1 and then find the eigen values of $A(NG_i)$.

Let

$$A(NG_1) = (\mu_{v_i v_j}, \gamma_{v_i v_j}, \kappa_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} (0, 0, 0) & (0.6, 0.25, 0.5) & (0.7, 0.2, 0.5) \\ (0.6, 0.25, 0.5) & (0, 0, 0) & (0, 0, 0) \\ (0.7, 0.2, 0.5) & (0, 0, 0) & (0, 0, 0) \end{bmatrix}$$

FIGURE 2. Neutrosophic subgraph NG_1

and

$$A(\mu_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.6 & 0.7 \\ 0.6 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.7 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad A(\gamma_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.25 & 0.2 \\ 0.25 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\text{and} \quad A(\kappa_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigen values of adjacency matrix $A(\mu_{v_i v_j})$ of membership degree $\mu_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\mu} = 0$, $\lambda_{2\mu} = 0.92$ and $\lambda_{3\mu} = -0.92$. Now find the absolute maximum $\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}$, which is 0.92. Similarly the eigen values of the adjacency matrix $A(\gamma_{v_i v_j})$ of indeterminacy degree $\gamma_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\gamma} = 0$, $\lambda_{2\gamma} = 0.32$ and $\lambda_{3\gamma} = -0.32$. Now find the average absolute value $\text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}$, which gives 0.43. Likewise the eigen values of the adjacency matrix $A(\kappa_{v_i v_j})$ of non-membership degree $\kappa_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\kappa} = 0$, $\lambda_{2\kappa} = 0.71$ and $\lambda_{3\kappa} = -0.71$. Now the absolute minimum value $\text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}$ results to 0. Thus $\text{Eig}(N(G_i)) = (\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}, \text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}, \text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}) = (0.92, 0.43, 0)$ where $\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}$ is the absolute maximum of Eigen values of $A(\mu_{v_i v_j})$, $\text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}$ is the absolute minimum of Eigen values of $A(\kappa_{v_i v_j})$ and $\text{Min } \lambda_{i\gamma}$ is the absolute minimum of Eigen values of $A(\gamma_{v_i v_j})$.

Similarly the subgraph $NG_2 = \delta(v_2)$ is as shown in Fig. 3.

The membership adjacency matrix $A(\mu_{v_i v_j})$ of NG_2 , the indeterminacy adjacency matrix $A(\gamma_{v_i v_j})$ and the non-membership adjacency matrix $A(\kappa_{v_i v_j})$ are as given below.

$$A(\mu_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.6 \\ 0.6 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad A(\gamma_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.25 \\ 0.25 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad A(\kappa_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The eigen values of adjacency matrix $A(\mu_{v_i v_j})$ of membership degree $\mu_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\mu} = 0.6$, $\lambda_{2\mu} = -0.6$ and absolute maximum $\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}$, is 0.6. Similarly the eigen values of the adjacency matrix $A(\gamma_{v_i v_j})$ of indeterminacy degree $\gamma_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\gamma} = 0.25$, $\lambda_{2\gamma} = -0.25$ and the average absolute value $\text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}$, is 0.25. Likewise the eigen values of the adjacency matrix $A(\kappa_{v_i v_j})$

FIGURE 3. subgraph NG_2

of non-membership degree $\kappa_{v_i v_j}$ are $\lambda_{1\kappa} = 0.5$, $\lambda_{2\kappa} = -0.5$ and the absolute minimum value $\text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}$ results to 0.5.

Thus

$$\text{Eig}(N(G_2)) = (\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}, \text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}, \text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}) = (0.6, 0.25, 0.5).$$

Considering the vertex V_3 we get the subgraph $N(G_3)$ as in Fig. 4.

FIGURE 4. subgraph $N(G_3)$

The three adjacency matrix

$$A(\mu_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.7 & 0 \\ 0.7 & 0 & 0.7 \\ 0 & 0.7 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ with eigen values } \lambda_{1\mu} = 0, \lambda_{2\mu} = 0.99 \text{ and } \lambda_{3\mu} = -0.99. \text{ The}$$

absolute 0 maximum $\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}$, is 0.99

$$A(\gamma_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.2 & 0 \\ 0.2 & 0 & 0.3 \\ 0 & 0.3 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ with eigen values } \lambda_{1\gamma} = 0, \lambda_{2\gamma} = 0.36 \text{ and } \lambda_{3\gamma} = -0.36. \text{ The}$$

average of absolute values gives 0.24

$$\text{and } A(\kappa_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.5 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 0 & 0.4 \\ 0 & 0.4 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ with eigen values } \lambda_{1\kappa} = 0, \lambda_{2\kappa} = 0.64 \text{ and } \lambda_{3\kappa} = -0.64. \text{ The}$$

absolute minimum gives 0. Now

$$\text{Eig}(N(G_3)) = (\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}, \text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}, \text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}) = (0.99, 0.24, 0).$$

Considering the vertex V_4 , we get the subgraph $N(G_4)$ as in Fig. 5.

FIGURE 5. Subgraph V_4

The adjacency matrices are $A(\mu_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.7 \\ 0.7 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ with eigen values $\lambda_{1\mu} = 0.7, \lambda_{2\mu} = -0.7$ and absolute maximum $\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}$, is 0.7.

$A(\gamma_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.3 \\ 0.3 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ with eigen values $\lambda_{1\gamma} = 0.3, \lambda_{2\gamma} = 0.3$ and the average of absolute values gives 0.3 and $A(\kappa_{v_i v_j}) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0.4 \\ 0.4 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ with eigen values $\lambda_{1\kappa} = 0.4, \lambda_{2\kappa} = -0.4$ and the absolute minimum gives 0.4. Now

$$\text{Eig}(N(G_4)) = (\text{Max } \lambda_{i\mu}, \text{Avg } \lambda_{i\gamma}, \text{Min } \lambda_{i\kappa}) = (0.7, 0.3, 0.4).$$

Let $G_{i,i=1,2,\dots}$ be subgraphs. Compare the Eigen values of adjacency matrices. Let the membership adjacency matrix be $A_\mu(G)$, indeterminacy membership adjacency matrix be $A_\gamma(G)$ and Non-membership matrix be $A_\kappa(G)$. Apply the following rules to add any new edges to the underlying graph.

- (1) Consider the subgraphs obtained and the given graph. Compare the absolute values of Eigen values of the membership adjacency matrices. Arrange these values in descending order. Consider the pairs of subgraphs with the corresponding eigen values ordered by $\lambda_i > \lambda_j$. If there exist atleast one edge which connects any two vertices of the two subgraphs then no need to add any new edges to the given graph.
- (2) If the subgraphs G_i and G_j are disconnected then join any vertex in G_i to a vertex in G_j .
- (3) Use any two vertices which were not connected in the previous step.

Compare the Eigen values. For $A(\mu_{v_i v_j})$, here, $0.99 > 0.92 > 0.7 > 0.6$ where $G_3 > G_1 > G_4 > G_2$. Check with all pairs of subgraphs and apply the above rule.

Consider the following pair wise connectivity for applying the above mentioned rules.

- (a) (G_3, G_4) —Vertices v_3 and v_4 are common to the sub graphs G_3, G_4 . So by rule 1, no modification is required.
- (b) (G_3, G_1) —Vertices v_3 and v_1 are common to the sub graphs G_3, G_1 . So by rule 1, no modification is required.

- (c) (G_3, G_2) —Vertex v_1 is common to the sub graphs G_3, G_2 . So by rule 1, no modification is required.
- (d) (G_4, G_1) —Vertex v_3 is common to the sub graphs G_4, G_1 . So by rule 1, no modification is required.
- (e) (G_4, G_2) There is no edge between G_4 and G_2 . Hence draw a new edge which connects a vertex in G_4 to a vertex in G_2 . So, draw an edge between v_2 and v_3 .
- (f) (G_1, G_2) —Vertices v_1 and v_2 are common to the sub graphs G_3, G_1 . So by rule 1, no modification is required.

Considering case (e) above, a new edge is to be added in the main graph G from subgraph G_4 to G_2 . The two nodes selected for this connection will be the two nearest ones among all possible pairs in two subgraphs G_4 and G_2 . The Euclidean distance between the (v_4, v_1) is 0.2236, between (v_3, v_1) is 0.3, between (v_3, v_2) is 0.1732, between (v_4, v_2) is 0.1732. Since both the pairs (v_3, v_2) and (v_4, v_2) are having the same distance, let us select any one out of it. Here we have selected the pair (v_3, v_2) . The modified Neutrosophic graph is shown in Fig. 6. And the red coloured edge is a new edge.

FIGURE 6. Modified neutrosophic graph. MG

Similarly compare the Eigen values of $A_\kappa(G)$ and $A_\gamma(G)$. Apply the previous steps to modify the graph. A graph renewal algorithm is given below.

Algorithm 1: Construction of the modified Neutrosophic graph:

- Step 1:* Let G_i, G_j, G_k, \dots be subgraphs of G .
- Step 2:* Calculate the Eigen values of the membership adjacency matrix $A_\mu(G)$, Indeterminacy matrix $A_\gamma(G)$ and Non membership matrix be $A_\kappa(G)$ and arrange these values in descending order.
- Step 3:* If $\lambda_i > \lambda_j$ then check whether the subgraphs are connected. Otherwise draw an edge from a vertex v_i in G_i to a vertex v_j in G_j .
- Step 4:* Repeat step 3 for the other pairs of subgraphs
- Step 5:* Obtain the transformed graph $G = \cup_i(G_i)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, G_i s are underlying subgraphs. Keep the same membership degree in the new graph also. This represent a transformed Neutrosophic graph.

1.2. δ -induced directed connected sub graphs

$\delta(v_i) = G_i, \delta(v_j) = G_j, \delta(v_k) = G_k$ be distinct Neutrosophic subgraphs which satisfies the condition (1). Let C_μ and C_κ denote the sum of membership degree and indeterminacy degree of each subgraph obtained. Then $C_{\mu+\gamma} = C_\mu + C_\gamma$.

$$\text{i.e., } C_\mu = \left[\sum [(\mu_{G_{S_i}})] \right] \text{ and } C_\gamma = \left[\sum (\gamma_{G_{S_j}}) \right]$$

If $C_{\mu+\gamma}^i > C_{\mu+\gamma}^j$ then G_i is a strong subgraph than G_j . There exist an edge connecting to $G_i, G_j, G_k. G_i \rightarrow G_j \Leftrightarrow \exists$ a path from $v_i \rightarrow v_j$.

Rule for converting the transformed IF graph into a directed Neutrosophic graph.

(a) Calculate $C_{\mu+\gamma}$ for each vertex v of the MG

$$\text{i.e. } C_{\mu+\gamma} = \left[\sum [(\mu_{(G_{S_i}, \gamma_{G_{S_j}})})] \right].$$

(b) If $C_{\mu+\gamma} > C_{\mu+\gamma}^j$ then v_i is a strong vertex than v_j and if $C_{\mu+\gamma}^i > C_{\mu+\gamma}^j$ then assign directions from higher valued vertex to the lower valued vertex. Here it is directed towards V_j .

Here, $C_{\mu+\gamma}^i = 2.6, C_{\mu+\gamma}^2 = 1.6, C_{\mu+\gamma}^3 = 1.4, C_{\mu+\gamma}^4 = 1.9$. So let the ordering be $V_1 > V_4 > V_2 > V_3$.

Hence assign directions w. r. to this order as shown in Fig. 7.

FIGURE 7. Directed Modified Neutrosophic graph

- i) $V_1 > V_2$. Hence assign directions from V_1 to V_2 .
- ii) $V_1 > V_3$. Hence assign directions from V_1 to V_3 .
- iii) $V_2 > V_3$. Hence assign directions from V_2 to V_3 .
- iv) $V_4 > V_3$. Hence assign directions from V_4 to V_3 .

Algorithm 2: Construction of δ -induced directed connected transformed Neutrosophic graphs

Step 1: Let V_i, V_j, V_k, \dots be the vertices of the transformed Neutrosophic graph.

Step 2: For each vertex, Calculate $C_{\mu+\gamma}$ which is the sum of membership degree and non membership degree.

Step 3: If $C_{\mu+\gamma}^i > C_{\mu+\gamma}^j$ then assign directions from vertex V_i to V_j .

Step 4: Repeat steps 2 to 3 until all edges are considered.

Step 5: Obtain a directed transformed Neutrosophic Graph.

2. Neutrosophic Graph Transformation

Definition: A Neutrosophic Graph can be modified by applying Morphological operators like dilation and erosion. This can be obtained with δ -induced or ϵ induced directed connected sub graphs. This is called a Neutrosophic Graph transformation. This may contain an addition of edges.

2.1. Definition: Neutrosophic Graph Space

(NG, \mathcal{M}) represent a family of Neutrosophic graph obtained by applying operators in \mathcal{M} , the set of Morphological operators, is called an Neutrosophic graph space. The Neutrosophic graph space is denoted by NG_M . Let the sub graphs of NG_M be $NG_{M1}, NG_{M2}, \dots, NG_{Mn}$.

2.2. Definition: \mathcal{M} induced sequence

The set of edges of $NG_{M1}, NG_{M2}, \dots, NG_{Mn}$ formed by taking the edges which lies in the intersection of any two subgraphs form a sequence of edges. This family of sequence of edges are called \mathcal{M} induced edge sequence and is denoted by $\mathfrak{E}_{M \cdot E}$ where $\mathfrak{E}_{M \cdot E} = \{\mathcal{E}_{M1}, \mathcal{E}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{Mn}\}$ where $\mathcal{E}_{M1} = \{e_{11} \cdot e_{12}, \dots, e_{1n}\}, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{Mn} = \{e_{n1} \cdot e_{n2}, \dots, e_{nn}\}$. Similarly for the vertices which lies in the intersection of any two sub graphs form an \mathcal{M} induced sequence of vertices and is denoted by \mathfrak{E}_{M_V} .

$$\mathfrak{E}_{M_V} == \mathcal{V}_{M1}, \mathcal{V}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{Mn}, \mathcal{V}_{M1} = v_{11} \dots v_{1n} \dots \mathcal{V}_{Mn} = \{v_{n1} \dots v_{nn}\}.$$

Maximal vertex Intersection Number: The Maximal intersection number of an \mathcal{M} induced vertex sequence is the number of sets having vertices common in $\mathcal{V}_{M1}, \mathcal{V}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{Mn}$. It is denoted by \mathcal{M}_τ . These numbers are useful for identifying a path or spanning trees in NG.

Maximal edge Intersection Number: The Maximal intersection number of an \mathcal{M} induced edge sequence is the number of sets having edges common in $\mathcal{E}_{M1}, \mathcal{E}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{Mn}$. It is denoted by \mathcal{M}_σ .

The path or spanning trees are obtained by considering the set of edges corresponding to this number.

Algorithm 3: Construction of \mathcal{M} induced sequences and directed spanning trees.

Step 1: Apply Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 to obtain a transformed directed NG with δ -induced or ϵ induced directed connected sub graphs.

Step 2: Find the sequences $\mathfrak{E}_{M_E} = \{\mathcal{E}_{M1}, \mathcal{E}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{Mn}\}$ and $\mathfrak{E}_{M_V} == \{\mathcal{V}_{M1}, \mathcal{V}_{M2}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{Mn}\}$.

Step 3: Find the Maximal intersection number and set of vertices.

Step 4: Find all directed spanning trees passing through the vertices which are common to these sets.

Illustration of the construction of a directed spanning tree:

Consider an M induced vertex sequence of the Neutrosophic graph and apply the procedure to generates various paths.

Here $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_1} = \{v_1, v_2, v_3\}$, $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_2} = \{v_1, v_2\}$, $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_3} = \{v_1, v_3, v_4\}$, $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_4} = \{v_3, v_4\}$. v_1 and v_3 are vertices having intersection in three sets. So, the **maximal intersection number** \mathcal{M}_τ is 3 and the intersection vertices are v_1, v_3 . The directed induced paths or directed spanning trees passing through these vertices are given below.

Spanning tree 1

Spanning tree 2

Spanning tree 3

Since any two edges in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\mathcal{E}}$ lies in the intersection of subgraphs, the corresponding union of subgraphs must contain various paths. Consider a directed NG_M . The consecutive edges from $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\mathcal{E}}$ induces a directed connected path.

Similarly, Since any two vertices in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}$ lies in the intersection of subgraphs, the corresponding union of subgraphs must contain various paths. Consider a directed NG_M . The consecutive vertices from $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}$ induces a directed connected path.

2.3. Definition: Neutrosophic Graph Morphological Network

NG_M with $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1}, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2}, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n}\}$, $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V} = \{\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_1}, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_2}, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_n}\}$ and Morphological operators in \mathcal{M} is called an Neutrosophic graph Morphological network and is denoted by $(NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$.

Since the collection of underlying subgraphs in NG_M form a lattice, there is an order relation between subgraphs and the related theories can be applied to $\{NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M}\}$ also. Minimum connected subgraph can be considered as infimum and the whole network which represents the supremum of the lattice. Since the underlying graph and subgraphs are connected by assumption, any two edges in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}$ or any two vertices in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}$ induces a path between any two vertices in the corresponding subgraphs. Hence $\{NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M}\}$ generates various paths between vertices in any two underlying subgraphs in NG_M .

This generates various directed spanning trees also.

2.4. Sequence of edges and vertices

The learning architecture of the sequence of edges in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}$ and vertices in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}$ can be obtained by considering a Morphological operator on the Neutrosophic graph Morphological network $(NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$.

Generalized \mathcal{M} induced vertex sequences and edge sequences

Let the number of subgraphs be n and the number of subgraphs for grouping is k where $k \leq n$.

Then the **Generalized \mathcal{M} induced vertex sequences and edge sequences** are $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V} = \{\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^k, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^k, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_n}^k\}$ and $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^k, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^k, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n}^k\}$.

Algorithm 4 : Construction of all possible trees

Step 1: Apply algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 on NG

Step 2: Apply Algorithm 3 with various values of k and obtain the sequences $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V} = \{\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^k, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^k, \dots, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_n}^k\}$ and $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^k, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^k, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n}^k\}$ where $k \leq n$.

Step 3: Find the **maximal intersection number \mathcal{M}_τ and related vertices**.

Step 4: Obtain all possible trees which are passing through these vertices. There may or may not be spanning Trees. The spanning trees obtained by considering various values of $k \leq n$ are called k level spanning trees and is denoted by S_n^k .

Example: Consider the case with $n = 4$, $k = 3$ and with $n = 4$, $k = 4$.

The possible combinations of subgraphs and its vertex sequences are given below:

Case 1) $n = 4, k = 3$.

For $(G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4), \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^3 = \{v_1\}, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^3 = \{v_3\}, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_3}^3 = \{\}, \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{M}_4}^3 = \{\}$.

No vertex is common to any of these sets in the induced vertex sequence $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V} = \{V_{\mathcal{M}_1}^3, V_{\mathcal{M}_2}^3, V_{\mathcal{M}_3}^3, V_{\mathcal{M}_4}^3\}$. Hence there is no spanning tree for $k = 3$. But a tree can be drawn through the vertices v_1, v_3 . Here $|S_n^k| = 0$.

Case 2) $n = 4, k = 4$

For (G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4) , no vertex is common to these subgraphs. Hence there is no spanning tree. Here $|S_n^k| = 0$.

Also there is no tree.

Therefore, there is no k level spanning tree connectivity between subgraphs for $k > 2$.

Proposition: If there exist k level spanning tree connectivity for every value of $k \leq n$ in the Neutrosophic graph Morphological network $(NG_{\mathcal{M}}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$ then the underlying graph is the union of all spanning trees.

Proof: Since $G_i = \delta(v_i)$ and if there exist k level spanning tree connectivity for every value of $k \leq n$ then the vertex sequence contains all the vertices of G and since various spanning trees exist which implies that the given graph is the union of all spanning trees obtained.

2.5. Directed Neutrosophic graph Morphological network

$(NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$ with a directed Morphological network is called **Directed Neutrosophic graph Morphological network and is denoted by $(NG_M^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$** , (DNG–MN). Consider $(NG_M, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$. Let $e_{11} \in \epsilon_{\mathcal{M}_1}, e_{12} \in \epsilon_{\mathcal{M}_1}$. Then e_{11}, e_{12} are consecutive edges means there exist a directed path containing these edges and there exist an underlying subgraph where these edges belong. Hence the consecutive edges form a directed path. It is denoted by $e_{ii} \approx e_{jj}$.

Let $e_{ii} \approx e_{jj}$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Then $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}}$ represent the set of all such directed paths and this will form a directed network.

2.6. Proposition

Consider $(NG_M^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_E}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_V}, \mathcal{M})$. If one edge in $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1}$ and one edge in $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2}$ are consecutive then there exist at least a path of length two.

Proof: By definition.

2.7. *Theorem*

$\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon} = \{\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1}^k, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2}^k, \dots, \mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n}\}$ with edges in $\mathcal{E}_{\mathcal{M}_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are consecutive then these consecutive edges generates a directed network.

Proof: By Proposition 2.8.

2.8. *Theorem: Minimal spanning tree*

Consider $(NG_{\mathcal{M}}^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}, \mathcal{M})$. Then $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}}$ induces a directed Minimal spanning tree where $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}}$ is the set of all paths obtained by using edges in $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}}$.

Proof: $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}}$ represent the set of all paths obtained by using edges in $\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}$. Hence this contain a minimal spanning tree.

2.9. *Theorem*

Let $(NG_{\mathcal{M}}^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}, \mathcal{M})$ be a Directed Neutrosophic graph Morphological network (DNG–MN). Then $\{\epsilon_{\mathcal{M}_i, e_{ij} \in \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_i}}\}$ induces a filtration.

Proof: Let $(NG_{\mathcal{M}}^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}, \mathcal{M})$ be a Directed Neutrosophic graph Morphological network (DNG–MN). By theorem, $(NG_{\mathcal{M}}^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}, \mathcal{M})$ induces a minimal spanning tree which represents a filtration.

2.10. *Sublevel filtration of network*

Each induced subgraphs represent sublevels. These sub graphs $\{G_i\}$ generates filtrations. Hence a network has an ordered filtrations. In such cases a starting vertex is assumed as a vertex which lies left and assume that the network levels are advancing towards right. Since the graph space is a lattice it induces a partial order relation and hence allows directions and movements in the navigation from left to right. If we choose a vertex in random then the ordering become a consensus ordering or permutation ordering. Different filtrations can be generated using different starting vertices. A Neutrosophic transformation can be applied to obtain a new vertex (a dummy vertex) so that various other ordering may be applied.

2.11. *Theorem*

$P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1, \varepsilon}} \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2, \varepsilon}} \preceq \dots \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n, \varepsilon}}$ is a filtration of the subgraphs G_1, \dots, G_n .

Proof: By applying the Decomposition theorem: $NG_{\mathcal{M}} = \cup_{i=1}^n NG_{\mathcal{M}_i}$ and apply proposition 2.8, theorem 2.9.

3. Application to Path planning and Disease detection

3.1. Path planning in a Directed Neutrosophic graph Morphological Network (DNG–MN)

Path planning in a graph like DNG–MN requires specific constraints. MST algorithms meet these requirements. However the method discussed in this paper gives another framework for a general search problems and path planning. Since the proposed method deals with subgraphs, the local search is also possible. Vertices which is common to any two subgraphs are important because they play a crucial role in the formulation of an optimal path in DNG–MN. These vertices are playing as linking t vertices in the sub graphs and this will generate various paths. This will be helpful for the analysis of diseases like cancer, alshimers etc.

3.2. Analogy with the brain neural network

Here we can consider the analogy with the brain network. Connections between brain regions do not have the same degree of adjacency. Regions can be converted to a DNG–MN $(NG_M^{\rightarrow}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\varepsilon}, \mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_\nu}, \mathcal{M})$ and obtain a filtration of the form $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1, \varepsilon}} \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2, \varepsilon}} \preceq \cdots \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n, \varepsilon}}$. This filtration will be helpful for the study of Brain neural network.

3.3. Algorithm 5: Brain Disease detection algorithm

Step 1: Consider the DNG–MN corresponding to the image of a brain network.

Step 2: Find the vertex dilation induced subgraphs $G_i = \delta(v_i)$.

Step 3: Calculate the Eigen values of $A_\mu(G)$, $A_\kappa(G)$ and $A_\nu(G)$ and arrange these values in descending order and apply algorithm 1 to obtain the transformed $N(G_i)$.

Step 4: Apply algorithm 2 to obtain a directed transformed NG.

Step 5: Apply algorithm 3 and 4 to obtain spanning trees and find a filtration in the underlying graph of DNG–MN of the form $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1, \varepsilon}} \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2, \varepsilon}} \preceq \cdots \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n, \varepsilon}}$.

Step 6: If there is no spanning trees then there is a chance of a disease in a region corresponding to any subgraphs.

3.4. Optimal network and flow of neurons

Consider a filtration in the underlying graph of DNG–MN of the form $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1, \varepsilon}} \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2, \varepsilon}} \preceq \cdots \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n, \varepsilon}}$. Let this be a filtration of the subgraphs G_1, \dots, G_n . Since each filtration is a spanning tree or paths, consider the maximum spanning tree in each subgraphs and then calculate the Span integrity [3] of these spanning tree/ paths. The Vertex Span integrity of DNG–MN with respect to dilation is defined as $(\text{Max } \mu_{\delta(v_i)} + S\mu_{G-\delta(v_i)}, \text{Min } \kappa_{\delta(v_i)} + S\kappa_{G-\delta(v_i)}, \text{Ave } \gamma_{\delta(v_i)} + S\gamma_{G-\delta(v_i)})$ where $\text{Max } \mu_{\delta(v_i)}$ is the maximum membership degree of a vertex w.r.to dilation of v_i , $\text{Min } \kappa_{\delta(v_i)}$, the minimum membership degree of a vertex w.r.to

dilation of v_i , $\text{Min } \gamma_{\delta(v_i)}$ is the average membership degree of a vertex w.r.to dilation of v_i and $S\mu_{G-\delta(v_i)}$ denotes the spanness [3] of $G-\delta(v_i)$ w. r.to membership degree, $S\kappa_{G-\delta(v_i)}$ is the spanness of $G-\delta(v_i)$ w. r.to the non membership degree and $S\gamma_{G-\delta(v_i)}$ denotes the spanness of $G-\delta(v_i)$ w. r.to the indeterminacy membership degree. Similarly we can define the edge span integrity. The reordering of paths can be done w. r.to the values obtained. In application point of view, the subgraph ordering will give the information about region of a brain to be prioritized.

Algorithm 6: Ordering of subgraphs using DNG–MN and span integrity

Step 1: Apply Algorithms 1,2,3 and obtain DNG–MN.

Step 2: Consider a filtration in the underlying graph of DNG–MN of the form $P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{E}}} \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_2, \mathcal{E}}} \preceq \dots \preceq P_{\mathfrak{E}_{\mathcal{M}_n, \mathcal{E}}}$.

Let this be a filtration of the subgraphs G_1, \dots, G_n .

Step 3: Find the maximum spanning tree in each subgraphs and then calculate the Span integrity [3] of these spanning tree/paths.

Step 4: Order the subgraphs w. r.to the values obtained. i) μ ordering- w.r.to membership degree ii) κ ordering—w.r.to non membership degree iii) γ ordering—indeterminacy degree.

Illustration: Consider a DNG–MN

$\text{Max } \mu_{\delta(v_1)}, \text{Min } \kappa_{\delta(v_1)}, \text{Ave } \gamma_{\delta(v_1)} = (0.7, 0.1, 0.5), S_{G-\delta(v_1)} = (1.4, 0.2)$. So the span integrity w.r.to the dilation of v_1 is $(2.1, 0.3)$. Similarly calculate the Span integrity for other vertices. This will give an idea about the strength of regions. So, this method is useful for the prediction diseases like brain diseases.

Subgraph	Max $\mu_{\delta(v_i)}, \text{Min } \kappa_{\delta(v_i)}, \text{Ave } \gamma_{\delta(v_i)}$	$S_{G-\delta(v_i)}$	Span Integrity
G_1	$(0.7, 0.1, 0.5)$	$(0.5, 0.3, 0.4)$	$(1.2, 0.4, 0.9)$
G_2	$(0.6, 0.1, 0.53)$	$(1.2, 0.6, 1.0)$	$(1.8, 0.7, 1.53)$
G_3	$(0.7, 0.1, 0.5)$	$(0.6, 0.4, 0.5)$	$(1.3, 0.5, 1.0)$
G_4	$(0.7, 0.3, 0.5)$	$(1.1, 0.5, 1.0)$	$(1.8, 0.8, 1.5)$

μ ordering—w.r.to membership degree: $G_2 = G_4 > G_3 > G_1$

κ ordering—w.r.to non membership degree: $G_1 < G_3 < G_2 < G_4$

γ ordering—w.r.to indeterminacy degree: $G_1 < G_3 < G_2 < G_4$.

4. Discussions

4.1. Data representation

Several computational complexities arise while implementing the morphological operators like dilation, erosion etc. on neutrosophic graphs [20]. Since the input to the proposed system are images, converting the image data to the neutrosophic graph requires a sophisticated data structure for storing and processing various attributes. Also three weights have to be added to each node and edge of the neutrosophic graph made out of the image data. This leads to more intense calculations. Since every node and edge has indeterminacy factor, this may affect computation of structural elements like connected components and boundaries. If the size of the neutrosophic graph increases, then scalability issue can occur and that in turn increase the algorithmic complexity. Addressing these challenges requires sophisticated algorithms.

4.2. AI and ML Technique

AI and ML technique can be included in this proposed method by developing a Graph Neural network(GNN) which can be designed such that the image neutrosophic graph can be given as the input to the GNN and spanning trees are obtained as output of the GNN. By including AI and ML techniques, we can handle the uncertainty factor leading to more accurate predictions and insightful analysis.

4.3. Decision making systems

In Directed Neutrosophic Graphs(DNG), the direction can be modeled as the flow of information in the decision making process. Real world decision making consists of many uncertainty, imprecision and incomplete information which are well addressed here. As mentioned in section 3.3, DNG can be used in medical diagnosis. This also finds application in social networking where the user interaction are uncertain and directions shows the followers in the social network. Directional dependencies in the supply chain management, share trade and market trends etc. all of which suffers from uncertainty can be modeled using DNG. Also careful modeling can be done in sustainable resource management and disaster management. Autonomous vehicles where the directional decisions are really important can be modeled as a DNG.

4.4. Optimization Methods

Just as alpha-beta pruning which is a common method in decision trees in AI, $T-I-F$ pruning can be included, which prunes the irrelevant sections in the DNG which are below the threshold values for $T-I-F$. This reduces the search time in the graph. Vertices with similar $T-I-F$ values

can be combined to a single vertex there by reducing the size of the graph. Parallel computing can be implemented by dividing the DNG in to subgraphs and processing them simultaneously using parallel systems.

5. Conclusion

A novel method to construct neutrosophic directed graphs is presented in this paper. Algorithms to construct induced subgraphs and spanning trees are given. The concept of \mathcal{M} induced sequences plays an important role in the study of Neutrosophic graphs. Filtration and DNG-MN are useful in the study of applications of Neutrosophic graphs. Some applications are also discussed in this paper. This work can be extended to the study of Neutrosophic graphs, Hypergraphs and Plithogenic Hyper graphs using other induced Morphological operators.

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